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Title:

“Quantum State Normalization in Z (Complex) Plane: A Geometric Interpretation”.

Abstract:

This conceptual paper presents a Geometric interpretation of Quantum State Normalization by relating Probability Amplitudes of a superposition to the Classical Model of a Unit Circle in the Z(Complex) Plane. Earlier work on “Existence and Non-Existence as Quantum Probabilities,” showed that the Normalization Condition $|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1$ is mathematically equivalent to the equation of a Unit Circle. This provides a powerful visual and intuitive framework for understanding Quantum Superposition, Quantum Normalization, Quantum Probability and Measurement/Observation.

$$|\Psi\rangle = \alpha|E\rangle + \beta|-E\rangle$$

More than that, the inclusion of Complex Phase factors is a deeper connection between the Z-Plane representation and Quantum State Evolution. By this approach which bridge formal Quantum Mechanics with accessible Geometric reasoning. This support learners or Students, Educators, Engineers and Researchers by visualizing abstract Quantum concepts. Like visualizing abstract Quantum principles as “Stability”.

1. Introduction:

This paper extends the idea presented in the previous work, "Existence and Non-Existence as Quantum Probability: A Probability-Based Alternative to Schrödinger's Cat" and "Quantum Superposition as Unit Circle: A Geometric View of Normalization". By exploring the Geometric interpretation of Quantum State Normalization using the Unit Circle in the Z(Complex) Plane.

Previous work:

"Existence and Non-Existence as Quantum Probability: A Probability-Based Alternative to Schrödinger's Cat".

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15421043>

"Quantum Superposition as Unit Circle: A Geometric View of Normalization".

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17198290>

The primary objective is to develop an intuitive understanding of Quantum Superposition by linking it with Classical Geometry. By interpreting Probability Amplitudes as Coordinates in the $Z(\text{Complex})$ Plane. Quantum States can be visualized as points on a Unit Circle, thereby simplifying abstract Mathematical concepts.

2. Mathematical Representation & State Formulation:

Let, $\alpha = a$ and $\beta = b$.

$$|z| = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}$$

$$\therefore z = r e^{j\theta} = r (\cos\theta + j\sin\theta)$$

Here, $r = 1$ [as Unit Circle (Previous Two Papers)]

$$\therefore z \cdot \bar{z} = (a + jb)(a - jb)$$

$$= a^2 - (jb)^2$$

$$= a^2 + b^2 = |z|^2$$

$$\therefore z \cdot \bar{z} = |z|^2$$

$$\therefore Z = r(\cos \theta + j \sin \theta)$$

$$r = \sqrt{1^2 + 1^2} = \sqrt{2}$$

$$\therefore \text{Arg}(Z) = \theta = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{1}\right) = \frac{\pi}{4}$$

$$\therefore Z = \sqrt{2} \left[\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) + j \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) \right]$$

$$\therefore Z = \sqrt{2} e^{j\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)}$$

Also,

Also,

$$\cos^2\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) + \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) = 1 \rightarrow \text{Unit Circle}$$

Quantum State of Existence and Non-Existence

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi\rangle &= \kappa e^{i\theta} |E\rangle + \kappa e^{-i\theta} |-E\rangle \\ &= \kappa e^{i(\frac{\pi}{4})} |E\rangle + \kappa e^{-i(\frac{\pi}{4})} |-E\rangle \end{aligned}$$

Z-Plane (Complex Plane) Representation of Quantum State

∴ From 'Quantum Superposition as Unit Circle':

$$\text{i.e. } |\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1$$

$$\therefore \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 = 1$$

Consider a Quantum State represented as a Superposition:

$$\text{As, } |\Psi\rangle = \alpha|E\rangle + \beta|-E\rangle$$

$$|\Psi\rangle = r e^{i(\theta)} |E\rangle + r e^{-i(\theta)} |-E\rangle$$

For Specific Phase, $\theta = \pi/4$ the State is represented as:

$$|\Psi\rangle = r e^{i(\pi/4)} |E\rangle + r e^{-i(\pi/4)} |-\!E\rangle$$

Now, by applying Conjugate identity

$$(a+jb)(a-jb) = |Z|^2$$

$$|\alpha|^2 = (1/\sqrt{2})^2 = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$|\beta|^2 = (1/\sqrt{2})^2 = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\therefore |\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} = 1.$$

Thus, Total Probability Density of the system is conserved at exactly 1.

$$\text{Also, } \sin^2(\pi/4) + \cos^2(\pi/4) = 1.$$

∴

$$|\Psi\rangle = r e^{i(\pi/4)} |E\rangle + r e^{-i(\pi/4)} |-\!E\rangle$$

$$Z = r e^{j(\pi/4)}$$

Notation and Cross-Domain Interpretation:

This paper is on a **Cross-Domain Framework** combining concepts from Quantum Mechanics and Engineering disciplines such as Signal & Systems and Control Theory. The Imaginary unit is denoted by i in Physics and j in Engineering, both represent $\sqrt{-1}$.

In this paper, i is used in Quantum Mechanical expressions and while j is used when referring to Z-Plane (Engineering) representations. This distinction allows a unified interpretation of Quantum States and Engineering System representations within a common Complex-Plane Framework.

3. Connection to the Unit Circle:

The Normalization Condition directly corresponds to the Unit Circle Equation:

$$x^2 + y^2 = 1.$$

Where,

$$x = |\alpha|$$

$$y = |\beta|$$

This establishes as a Geometric Analogy:

Every Normalized Quantum State corresponds to a point on the Unit Circle.

The Amplitudes $|\alpha|$ and $|\beta|$ act as projections on the Real and Imaginary axes.

4. Interpretation:

This Geometric Model provides several conceptual insights:

- **Superposition:**

A Quantum State is represented as a point on the Unit Circle that indicating Coexistence of Multiple States before Measurement/Observation.

- **Probability:**

The Squared Magnitudes $|\alpha|^2$ and $|\beta|^2$ correspond to Measurable Probabilities.

- **Phase:**

The angle (θ) represents Phase, which give an idea about interference effects in Quantum Systems.

- **Measurement/Observation (Collapse):**

Measurement/Observation can be Visualized as a projection of the State onto one Axis, resulting in a definite outcome.

This Interpretation Bridges abstract Quantum Formalism with intuitive Geometric Visualization.

5. Conclusion:

By linking Quantum Normalization with the Unit Circle in the Z(Complex)- Plane. We obtain a clear and intuitive representation of Quantum Superposition. This approach does not replace formal Quantum Mechanics but it provides a Geometric perspective that enhances understanding.

So, by linking Quantum Normalization with the Unit Circle, is an accessible perspective on the behaviour of Superposition State. The combination of Geometry and Probability act as a "Bridge" for Engineers and Physicists.

6. Potential Applications: A Cross-Domain Framework.

The Geometric Interpretation of Quantum State Normalization may have potential applications across both in Physics and Engineering domain.

- **Quantum State Visualization:**

The Unit Circle representation provides an intuitive way to visualize Superposition States and Probability Amplitudes. This support conceptual understanding.

- **Signals & Systems Analogy:**

The similarities between Complex Amplitude in Quantum Mechanics and Z-plane representation in Signals & Systems i.e. a conceptual bridge for analysing Phase and System behaviour.

- **Control Theory Perspective:**

In a Cross-Domain Framework, the bounded nature of Normalized Quantum States on the Unit Circle may be viewed as an analogous to Stability Region in Control Theory.

- **Electronics Perspective:**

From an Electronics Engineering perspective, when the condition $r = 1$ ("Quantum Superposition as Unit Circle: A Geometric View of Normalization") represents a marginally Stability indicating sustained Oscillation. In this Geometric

Framework, Normalized Quantum State also lie on the Unit Circle ($r=1$), that's indicating constant Probability Magnitude.

This analogy suggests a conceptual connection to Oscillatory Phenomena (*Oscillator*) such as Simple Harmonic Motion and Fourier Analysis representation, where Complex Exponential describe Periodic behaviour. While this does not have any physical evidence but it provides an Intuitive Bridge between Quantum State evolution and Classical Signals Analysis.

Acknowledgments:

I would like to express gratitude to the Educators, Engineers, Physicists, Mathematicians and P.R. Sir whose foundational work in Engineering Mathematics, Signals & Systems, Control Theory, Electronics, Quantum Mechanics and Geometric interpretation has inspired this extension.

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